

Maternal Mortality Rate, Risk Factors and Causes

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ABSTRACT

Objective: Purpose to conduct this study was to determine maternal mortality rate, its causes and associated risk factors.

Place and Duration: This study was conducted in Gynecology and Obstetrics Unit of Shifa international hospital Islamabad Pakistan from January 2017 to December 2017.

Design of Study: It was a descriptive study.

Patients and Methods: This study was conducted on the Obstetric patients admitted in Gynae ward via OPD and emergency bases during one year period. Total 1550 deliveries took place during this period and out of them 44 maternal deaths were recorded due to various causes. A predesigned proforma was used to document all necessary data of individual patients. At the time of presentation age, parity, previous history of still birth or abortion, mode of admission and history of previously mode of delivery either cesarean or vaginal delivery, eclampsia, hemorrhage, sepsis, obstructed labour, Anemia, other morbidities like renal failure or heart disease all data was documented on the proforma. A written consent was taken from all the patients for including them in the study. Proper consent was also taken from the Medical superintendent of the hospital. All laboratory investigations and ultrasound were done from within the hospital. These patients were monitored continuously.

Results: During study period 1550 deliveries conducted in gynae. and obs. ward of the Hospital. Out of them 44 mothers died due to various reasons. Maternal mortality rate was 28 per 1000 live births. Age range of these cases was 16-38 years with mean age of 18.5 years. Most of the cases 38.6% were having age of 26-30 years, 20.4% were in age group of 15-20 years, 27.2% with age of 21-25 and 13.6% mothers were above 30 years of age. Most common cause of mortality among mothers was eclampsia 25% followed by other causes such as hemorrhage 22.7%, sepsis 18%, obstructed labour 13.8%. These all were direct causes of mortality. Indirect causes include Liver disease 6.8%, anemia 9.1% and renal failure in 4.5%. Most of these cases had history of previous C-section single or multiple times in 50%, spontaneous vaginal delivery in 34% and still birth in 9% cases. Most of these mothers 45.4% were having 1-2 parity, 31.8% with zero parity and 22.7% with 3-4 parity.

Conclusion: There is high rate of maternal mortality in underdeveloped countries. Major risk factor is eclampsia followed by hemorrhage, sepsis and obstructed labour. Proper antenatal follow-up, proper history taking and thorough examination with vital monitoring can reduce the rate.

Key Words: maternal mortality, risk factors, hemorrhage, eclampsia

INTRODUCTION

Maternal mortality rate is an indicator of development of any country and its quality of health system. It is defined as death of a mother during pregnancy or 42 days after termination of pregnancy is called maternal mortality.¹ These deaths are related to pregnancy not from any trauma or accident. In underdeveloped and developing countries rate of maternal mortality is high as compared to developed countries where health system is much advanced and there are good policies in this regard. According to a report about five hundred thousand women die each year all over the world.² Previous studies showed maternal mortality of Karachi and Balochistan as 281 and 653 respectively.^{3,4} There are many causes of maternal death during pregnancy or just after completion of it such as sepsis, eclampsia, complicated delivery or abortions etc.⁵ In our country there is lack of education and due to high illiteracy rate mothers are not well aware about safety measures during pregnancy. False beliefs and misconceptions about pregnancy related issues contribute to development of complications and ultimate deaths of mothers. The Shifa Hospital where this study was done, receives many patients from the city and peripheral areas as well. Major proportion of patients is illiterate. Minority is educated people. This hospital is equipped with all necessary facilities and it is much developed healthcare center dealing with all medical and surgical specialties. Literacy rate and awareness in the community and specially among females play major role in determining maternal mortality rate. Mortality rate increases with the increase of age of mother as more complications of pregnancy develop in old mothers as compared to young mothers. Increases in parity also increases mortality rate this is due to multiple cesarean operations done previously make mother weak for further operations and such cases develop post op sepsis and more complications. It was seen that which mothers had more than two children they had high risk of mortality. There were two types of risk factors direct and indirect. In direct causes eclampsia is a most common risk factor of maternal mortality. This is a complication of pregnancy due

to uncontrolled hypertension in which seizures develop and patient die due to cardio respiratory failure. Second most common factor is hemorrhage either antipartum or post partum hemorrhage. This leads to massive blood loss, hypotensive shock and death. Post partum sepsis is very common in underdeveloped healthcare settings or where deliveries are done in unsterilized environment. Septic environment causes infection of mother and child as well and leads to maternal and neonatal sepsis. Obstructed labour is another direct risk factor of maternal mortality.

PATIENTS AND METHODS

This is a descriptive study done at a tertiary care hospital during a period of one year. This study was conducted in Gynae and Obs unit of the hospital. Only those cases were included which were admitted in the hospital. Total 1550 deliveries took place during this period and out of them 44 maternal deaths were recorded due to various causes. A predesigned proforma was used to document all necessary data of individual patients. At the time of presentation age, parity, previous history of still birth or abortion, mode of admission and history of previously mode of delivery either cesarean or vaginal delivery, eclampsia, hemorrhage, sepsis, obstructed labor, Anemia, other morbidities like renal failure or heart disease all data was documented on the proforma. A written consent was taken from all the patients for including them in the study. Proper consent was also taken from the Medical superintendant of the hospital. All laboratory investigations and ultrasound were done from within the hospital. These patients were monitored continuously. There are much qualified and competent gynecologists in the ward which deal with complicated cases daily. Operation Theater is well equipped with advance facilities and machinery. Laparoscopic facility is also available in the operation theater. Hospital has its own laboratory where almost all types of tests are done. Data of all mothers who died was collected and possible risk factors were evaluated. Each and every case was fully studied for risk factors and possible causes of complications. Operation theaters of this hospital are well sterilized and neat and clean. So chances of sepsis are very low here. But many patients are reported here after getting cesarean or spontaneous delivery in other health set-ups and present with complications due to faulty techniques or improper methods of delivery and septic environments of those hospitals where operation was done previously.

RESULTS

Data of all mothers who died was collected and possible risk factors were evaluated. Each and every case was fully studied for risk factors and possible causes of complications. During study period 1550 deliveries conducted in gynae. and obs. ward of the Hospital. Out of them 44 mothers died due to various reasons. Maternal mortality rate was 28 per 1000 live births. Age range of these cases was 16-38 years with mean age of 18.5 years. Most of the cases 38.6% were having age of 26-30 years, 20.4% were in age group of 15-20 years, 27.2% with age of 21-25 and 13.6% mothers were above 30 years of age. Most common cause of mortality among mothers was eclampsia 25% followed by other causes such as hemorrhage 22.7%, sepsis 18%, obstructed labour 13.8%. These all were direct causes of mortality. Indirect causes include Liver disease 6.8%, anemia 9.1% and renal failure in 4.5%. Most of these cases had history of previous C-section single or multiple times in 50%, spontaneous vaginal delivery in 34% and still birth in 9% cases. Most of these mothers 45.4% were having 1-2 parity, 31.8% with zero parity and 22.7% with 3-4 parity. Mortality was common in old age mothers with age above 35 years. About 22.7% cases of maternal mortality were having children more than two while 31.8% were nulliparous and 45.4% had 1-2 children. Three patients died due to hepatic encephalopathy, 4 patients died due to anemia and 2 cases died due to renal failure. About 50% cases were undergone emergency C-section and 34% had spontaneous vaginal delivery. While 16% did not deliver and they died before delivery.

(figure-1) Different Modes of delivery in females of study group

(Table-1) Maternal mortality related to age of mothers.

(Table-1) Causes of Maternal Mortality among study group.

Causes of Maternal Mortality	Maternal deaths (n)	(%)
Anemia	4	9.1
Livr disease	3	6.8
Kidney Failure	2	4.5
Hypertension	11	25
Hemorrhage	10	22.7
Obstruction of Labour	6	13.8
Sepsis	8	18.1
Total number of deaths	44	100

DISCUSSION

During the period of pregnancy many physiological changes occur in mothers. There are some complications related to pregnancy which can be prevented by taking proper measures and life of baby and mother can be saved. According to a report MMR of developed countries like USA and UK etc was 20/100000 and maternal mortality rate of underdeveloped countries like Afghanistan was 1600/100000.^{8,9} Maternal mortality rate is an indicator of development of any country and its quality of health system. It is defined as death of a mother during pregnancy or 42 days after termination of pregnancy is called maternal mortality. These deaths are related to pregnancy not from any trauma or accident. In underdeveloped and developing countries rate of maternal mortality is high as compared to developed countries where health system is much advanced and there are good policies in this regard. According to a report about five hundred thousand women die each year all over the world. Previous studies showed maternal mortality of Karachi and Balochistan as 281 and 653

respectively. There are many causes of maternal death during pregnancy or just after completion of it such as sepsis, eclampsia, complicated delivery or abortions etc. In our country there is lack of education and due to high illiteracy rate mothers are not well aware about safety measures during pregnancy. False beliefs and misconceptions about pregnancy related issues contribute to development of complications and ultimate deaths of mothers. In our study Maternal mortality rate was 25/1000 this result is much similar to the studies done in Pakistan previously.¹⁰⁻¹² MMR is very high in Pakistan as compared to other developing countries like India, Iran and Turkey etc. This is a descriptive study done at a tertiary care hospital during a period of one year. This study was conducted in Gynae and Obs unit of the hospital. Only those cases were included which were admitted in the hospital. Total 1550 deliveries took place during this period and out of them 44 maternal deaths were recorded due to various causes. A predesigned proforma was used to document all necessary data of individual patients. At the time of presentation age, parity, previous history of still birth or abortion, mode of admission and history of previously mode of delivery either cesarean or vaginal delivery, eclampsia, hemorrhage, sepsis, obstructed labor, Anemia, other morbidities like renal failure or heart disease all data was documented on the proforma. A written consent was taken from all the patients for including them in the study. Proper consent was also taken from the Medical superintendant of the hospital. All laboratory investigations and ultrasound were done from within the hospital. These patients were monitored continuously. Each and every case was fully studied for risk factors and possible causes of complications. Operation theaters of this hospital are well sterilized and neat and clean. So chances of sepsis are very low here. But many patients are reported here after getting cesarean or spontaneous delivery in other health set-ups and present with complications due to faulty techniques or improper methods of delivery and septic environments of those hospitals where operation was done previously. Proper consent was also taken from the Medical superintendant of the hospital. All laboratory investigations and ultrasound were done from within the hospital. These patients were monitored continuously. There are much qualified and competent gynecologists in the ward which deal with complicated cases daily. According to another study done in Sri Lanka maternal mortality rate is 57/100000.¹⁸

Conclusion:

Education level of mothers is a very important factor determining mortality rate. There is high rate of

maternal mortality in underdeveloped countries. Major risk factor is eclampsia followed by hemorrhage, sepsis and obstructed labour. Proper

antenatal follow-up, proper history taking and thorough examination with vital monitoring can reduce the rate.

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